

E-SPLIT: A Hierarchical Genetic Algorithm for Energy-Efficient Distributed AI Services

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Abstract

As we progress toward a new era of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-enabled wireless networks, the focus shifts to deploying distributed intelligence to enhance network automation, scalability, and responsiveness. Despite its merits, it often leads to resource-intensive deployments, which raise energy concerns. These concerns are further amplified by the limited availability of resource orchestration strategies capable of addressing the multi-faceted nature of distributed AI. This work targets energy consumption minimization of distributed AI services by proposing a custom meta-heuristic, two-tier hierarchical genetic algorithm (HGA) that integrates a divide-and-conquer strategy to provide effective chained decision-making. The first tier of HGA determines the optimal placement of model partitions within an AI service on the underlying network, while the second tier focuses on strategic resource allocation for each partition, ensuring that service latency requirements are met. A safe strategy selection is proposed, applying a custom repair mechanism and a penalty function that discourages constraints violation. Evaluation results show the effectiveness and robustness of the proposed HGA, compared to two state-of-the-art baseline solutions, on different network environments and evaluation scenarios. HGA achieves up to 94.1% decrease in the total energy consumption per service compared to the baselines, while entirely eliminating infeasible strategies.

Keywords: 6G, Energy Efficiency, Service Placement, Resource Allocation, Genetic Algorithm, Distributed AI

1. Introduction

As technology moves from 5G and Beyond 5G (B5G) to 6G networks, a clear transition from operator- to user-centric paradigms is observed [1]. This paradigm shift is triggered by the wide proliferation of *smart* devices (ranging from smartphones to industrial robots) [2, 3] and the need to support new and challenging use cases and applications [4]. In response to this paradigm shift, unprecedented and innovative concepts emerge, focusing on decentralized and distributed intelligence across the network, enabling collaborative operation of heterogeneous network systems (e.g., deep edge, edge, cloud) and dynamic service adaptation. This shift necessitates novel distributed approaches to Artificial Intelligence (AI), leveraging the capabilities of 6G networks, in order to enhance system automation and proactive adaptation, as well as effective resource management across the device–edge–cloud computing continuum. Such Distributed AI approaches typically rely on *model splitting/partitioning*, where AI models of reduced computational complexity are shared among (in general heterogeneous) devices, enhancing scalability and reducing network delays [5].

Since the publication of Rel. 18 and 19 of the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), there has been an attempt to adopt distributed AI by introducing multiple distributed Network Data Analytics Functions (NWDAFs) and incorporating the Model Training Logical Function (MTLF) [6], while investigating AI model transfer mechanisms for flexible deployment and management [7, 8].

Despite its apparent advantages and the undertaken significant standardization efforts, distributed AI has not yet experienced the anticipated large-scale adoption due to the energy concerns that are intensified as the number of the engaged connected devices increases exponentially. These concerns are exacerbated by a recent study [9] that estimates a global data center electricity use of about 415 TWh in 2024 (about 1.5% of global demand) and is projected to more than double, reaching about 945 TWh by 2030. AI-accelerated servers alone grow at about 30% annually and account for nearly half of the aforementioned electricity growth. In the USA, AI-associated data centers may be responsible for almost half of total electricity demand growth by 2030.

Several critical challenges related to the application of distributed AI to wireless networks have already been identified, significantly affecting the overall energy consumption of the involved devices [10]. Firstly, distributed

AI models partitioned and shared across the network require frequent transmissions between computing devices. Such transmissions may include high dimensional intermediate model outputs of complex neural network architectures comprising millions or even billions of parameters (e.g. Transformers [11]), imposing a significant communication burden.

On one hand, periodically transmitting large volumes of updates imposes notable energy demands on the computing devices. On the other hand, network delays are introduced since the required communication channel capacity increases proportionally to the number of computing devices and model partitions. Consequently, the smooth operation of a distributed AI process may be significantly impacted, particularly in dynamic network environments with time-varying conditions (e.g., in terms of channel quality and traffic loads), thereby necessitating effective resource management and model partition placement within the underlying network infrastructure. Secondly, AI model architectures require calculations whose complexity and intensity is tightly related to the size of the model and the selected model partitioning. Consequently, model size and partitioning strongly affect the energy demands. Finally, the stringent AI performance (e.g., low response times) required by critical services and applications [12], in conjunction with the computing heterogeneity across the engaged devices, call for high resource availability and energy consumption. As a result, resources should be allocated and orchestrated considering energy consumption issues, as well.

Motivated by the open research challenges, this study proposes a novel, energy-efficient framework capable of joint multi-service *placement* and *execution*, considering AI model partitioning and ensuring compliance with AI service delay requirements. More specifically, we propose a custom meta-heuristic two-tier hierarchical genetic algorithm (HGA) that adopts a divide-and-conquer strategy, splitting the original complex problem into two sequentially interdependent sub-problems of reduced computational complexity. The *placement* sub-problem refers to selecting devices capable of executing AI model partitions, while the *execution* sub-problem refers to allocating resources to each model partition. The proposed solution considers dynamicity in the network environment and the involved devices (in terms of resource availability and AI service execution capabilities). It encompasses the ever increasing complexity of an AI model that can significantly affect the overall energy consumption of a system. In ever-changing network environments, feasible solutions may be sparse. As a result, our approach enforces feasibility by introducing custom repair operators and penalty functions contributing

to a *safe* strategy selection.

Contribution: The key contributions of our two-tier HGA are summarized below:

- We target energy-efficient distributed AI service deployment and execution, while respecting service latency requirements.
- We focus on joint multi-service placement, considering AI model partitioning, while providing per-partition resource allocation decisions.
- We provide dynamic strategies adapted to service availability, time-varying device computational and communication resources, and network conditions.
- AI model complexity is integrated into both energy consumption and service end-to-end latency toward an AI focused system model and problem formulation.
- Our approach includes topology- and delay-aware path selection between consecutive partitions to further decrease energy consumption and service latency.
- We contribute to a *safe* strategy selection by enforcing solution feasibility with custom repair operators in conjunction with a custom penalty function that both prevent hard- and minimize soft- constraint violations.
- We target per-service energy minimization to contribute toward fairness across AI service deployment.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents relevant state-of-the-art works. Section 3 provides the system model. Section 4 provides the problem formulation. Section 5 describes key definitions along with the proposed solution that is evaluated in Section 7 using the simulation setup of Section 6. Finally, Section 8 concludes the paper.

2. Related Work

The ever-increasing use of *energy-hungry* Artificial Intelligence (AI) in future wireless networks has led to the development of energy-efficient deployment strategies. Recent research has focused on optimizing the placement of AI services and the allocation of computational and communication resources toward energy-efficient AI service deployment, while maintaining

service performance. Key approaches include joint optimization of service placement and offloading, energy-efficient strategies for AI model partitioning and placement, and AI-driven solutions for dynamic resource management in cloud, edge and hybrid environments.

Several research works have focused on AI service placement to enable efficient training and/or inference without explicit resource allocation. In [13] the authors model the problem of energy-efficient placement of services for AI applications as a multi-period optimization problem. They propose a heuristic approach to jointly place services and schedules requests targeting an overall energy consumption and latency minimization. The work [14] tackles the problem of efficiently allocating AI models by selectively offloading parts of inference tasks between devices and edge servers under given time and energy constraints. The authors in [15] propose Harmony, a deep reinforcement learning-driven Machine Learning (ML) cluster scheduler that places heterogeneous training jobs in a manner that minimizes average job completion time while respecting server capacities. Placement is decided per scheduling interval and then kept fixed until training job completion. Work [16] proposes a framework to place devices for distributed ML so as to reduce energy while maintaining performance. It evaluates placements by jointly considering energy costs, computational load, and data transfer, using both simulations and analytical studies.

Another group of research works study the problem of joint AI service placement and efficient resource allocation focusing on energy and latency as performance indicators. Work in [17] focuses on minimizing the total computing time and energy consumption of all task nodes and maximize the inference accuracy of AI tasks by jointly optimizing the resource allocation and computing offloading decision of each node by solving a mixed-integer non-linear programming (MINLP) problem. They propose an ADMM (alternating direction multiplier method)-based approach, decomposing the initial complex problem into smaller subproblems, enabling scalable optimization for large networks. The authors in [18] focus on joint optimization of task offloading, resource allocation, and placement AI models as a whole (no model partitioning is considered) in 6G networks, to enable efficient AI-as-a-Service (AIaaS), aiming to minimize a weighted system cost that combines latency, energy consumption, and service utility. A Lyapunov-based optimization is proposed toward solution scalability. Work [19] tackles the joint AI service placement and resource allocation in a multi-user MEC system to minimize each user's computation time and energy. The authors propose an ADMM method that

decomposes the problem into per-user parallel subproblems and use meta-heuristics for placement strategies. [20] introduces an Edge AI-as-a-Service framework that enables configurable deployment of AI models across edge servers to optimize delay, energy consumption, and AI result quality (e.g., accuracy or confidence). Authors of [21] propose a reinforcement-learning-based solution that captures task offloading, resource allocation, and model placement decisions to minimize system energy consumption under latency and resource constraints. Work [22] targets long term average device energy minimization for multi-partition Deep Neural Networks inference, while respecting resource limits. In addition, [23] proposes a reinforcement-learning approach that learns generalizable device-placement policies for distributed training, targeting the end-to-end execution time of a training step.

A set of works considers model partitioning to their placement and/or resource allocation decisions. Work [24] proposes an operator-fusion-aware device-placement method for distributed inference on heterogeneous devices to minimize end-to-end latency. In [25], the SplitPlace framework is proposed that uses a Multi-Armed Bandit selection for layer- or semantic- based model splitting and places the resulting partitions on edge workers using decision-aware reinforcement learning. The goal is to jointly improve accuracy while reducing response time. The study [26] focuses on minimizing energy consumption of vision transformers (models of high complexity), while maintaining acceptable model accuracy and latency, using dynamic complexity adjustment, task redistribution, and resource-aware partitioning.

Last but not least, works [27, 28, 29] focus on efficient resource management for a specific distributed AI framework, named Federated Learning, focusing on energy minimization, while considering targeted computation and communication requirements introduced in the training process.

Despite the extensive past work, there are still major challenges to be addressed. Most prior works handle AI service as a non-divisible block, without considering model partitioning and/or per-partition resource allocation and ignoring inter-service dependencies. Even works that tackle model partitioning mostly focus on a single AI service, excluding joint multi-service optimization. In addition, works that focus on joint service placement and efficient resource allocation fail to consider service, device and network dynamics, assuming static AI models and non time-varying conditions. Service activation/de-activation, time-varying resource availability and communication channel conditions can significantly affect the decision-making and should be part of the research scope. To the best of our knowledge this is the

first work that proposes an energy-efficient framework for joint multi-service placement and execution, considering AI model partitioning and imposed service delay thresholds. Our approach explicitly accounts for network and device dynamicity, as well as the impact that the growing complexity of AI models has on system energy consumption. To ensure solutions' feasibility, we introduce custom repair operators and penalty functions, yielding a safe strategy selection mechanism.

3. System Model

This section provides the system model of a distributed AI-enabled wireless network topology using AI model partitioning. AI model partitioning is a distributed technique that allows the division of a complex AI architecture into multiple, less complex partitions. This process enables the distribution of operations across numerous network devices, thereby enabling collaborative AI model execution while mitigating computational and communication overloads.

3.1. Network Topology

The network topology is modeled as an undirected graph $G(N, E)$, where N is a set of network devices and E is a set of bidirectional wireless links connecting them. Each device and link is characterized by computational and communication resources that vary over time. The time is divided into discrete time units, named time steps, and denoted by t .

Device Computational Capability: Let $u_n^{(t)} \in \mathbb{N}$, $f_n^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}_+$, $m_n^{(t)} \in \mathbb{N}$, and $d_n^{(t)} \in \mathbb{N}$ denote the available number of CPU cores, the CPU speed (in Hz), the memory and disk size (in *bits*) of device n at time step t . As a result, each device at each time step t is represented as a resource quadruple $R_n^{(t)} = \{u_n^{(t)}, f_n^{(t)}, m_n^{(t)}, d_n^{(t)}\}$. The CPU of each device n has also an effective switched capacitance, denoted by $\varsigma_n \in \mathbb{R}_+$, which depends on the hardware architecture. Based on $f_n^{(t)}$, device n can complete a certain number of FLOPs per cycle, denoted by $a_n^{(t)}$.

Device Communication Capability: Each wireless link $e_{(k,l)} \in E$ at timestep t , connects a pair of devices $k, l \in N$, and is modeled as a flat-fading channel with a constant Gaussian noise power spectral density $N_{0e} \in \mathbb{R}_+$ (in *Watts/Hz*), an achievable data rate $r_{e_{(k,l)}}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}_+$ (in *bps*) and a channel gain $g_{e_{k,l}}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}$ (*linear*). In addition, each source device k of a link $e_{(k,l)}$

has time-varying communication characteristics. These include the available bandwidth $\mathbf{b}_{e(k,l)}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}_+$ (in *Hz*), the antenna frequency $\mathbf{f}_{e(k,l)}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}_+$ (in *Hz*) and transmission power $\mathbf{tx}_{e(k,l)}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}_+$ (in *Watts*) at time step t .

3.2. Distributed AI Services

At each time step t , a set of $K^{(t)}$ AI services must be deployed over the underlying network topology with appropriate resource allocation to ensure efficient operation. Let $S^{(t)} = \{s_1^{(t)}, s_2^{(t)}, \dots, s_{K^{(t)}}^{(t)}\}$ denote the set of AI services to be deployed at time step t . We consider that each AI service $s_i^{(t)} \in S^{(t)}$ is divided into a sequence of L_i sequentially connected model partitions denoted by $P_{s_i}^{(t)} = \{p_{1,s_i}^{(t)}, \dots, p_{L_i,s_i}^{(t)}\}$. Each AI service imposes an end-to-end delay threshold $T_{s_i}^{thr(t)}$ to avoid undesirable service responsiveness.

The j^{th} model partition $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)} \in P_{s_i}^{(t)}$ of service s_i is characterized by a set of resource and data requirements denoted by $\mathbf{R}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$, where $\mathbf{R}_{j,s_i}^{(t)} = \{\mathbf{m}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}, \mathbf{i}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}, \mathbf{o}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}, \mathbf{d}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}, \mathbf{c}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}\}$. This set of requirements includes the model partition size $\mathbf{m}_{j,s_i}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{N}$ (i.e. the trainable parameters) (in *bits*), the data input shape $\mathbf{i}_{j,s_i}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{N}$, the output shape $\mathbf{o}_{j,s_i}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{N}$, the sample size precision $\mathbf{d}_{j,s_i}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{N}$ (e.g. 16, 32) (in *bits*), and the model partition complexity $\mathbf{c}_{j,s_i}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}_+$ (in *FLOPs*).

Partition Computational Cost: The processing of a partition $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ at device n introduces a computational cost to the network. This cost is based on the computation time $T_{j,s_i,n}^{comp(t)} \in \mathbb{R}_+$ (in *seconds*) and energy $E_{j,s_i,n}^{comp(t)} \in \mathbb{R}_+$ (in *Joules*) required by device n to process the partition. Both the computation time and energy depend on the available resources $R_n^{(t)}$ of device n at time step t (see Section 4 for more details).

Partition Communication Cost: Following the execution of a partition $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$, its output $\mathbf{o}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ must be transmitted to the device hosting the subsequent partition $p_{j+1,s_i}^{(t)}$. Let n_s and n_d denote the source and destination devices hosting partitions $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ and $p_{j+1,s_i}^{(t)}$, respectively. A communication cost is introduced to the network when transmitting across each wireless link $e \in E$ that belongs to the path connecting the host devices of the two subsequent partitions at time step t . This cost is shaped by the transmission time $T_{(j,j+1; n_s, n_d), s_i}^{tran(t)} \in \mathbb{R}_+$ (in *seconds*) and energy $E_{(j,j+1; n_s, n_d), s_i}^{tran(t)} \in \mathbb{R}_+$ (in *Joules*) required (see Section 4 for more details).

Table 1 summarizes the system model notations.

Parameter	Description
G	Undirected graph of network topology
N	Set of network devices in network topology G
E	Set of wireless links in network topology G
t	Timestep, a discrete time unit
$R_n^{(t)}$	Set of available computational resources of network device n at time step t
$u_n^{(t)}$	Available CPU cores of network device n at time step t
$f_n^{(t)}$	Available CPU speed of network device n at time step t
$m_n^{(t)}$	Available memory size of network device n at time step t
$d_n^{(t)}$	Available disk size of network device n at time step t
ς_n	Effective switched capacitance of network device n
$a_n^{(t)}$	Total number of FLOPs per cycle that network device n can complete at time step t
N_{0e}	Gaussian noise power spectral density of wireless link e
$r_{e_{(k,l)}}^{(t)}$	Achievable data rate of source node of wireless link $e_{(k,l)}$ at time step t
$g_{e_{(k,l)}}^{(t)}$	Channel gain of wireless link $e_{(k,l)}$ at time step t
$\mathbf{b}_{e_{(k,l)}}^{(t)}$	Available bandwidth of source node of wireless link $e_{(k,l)}$ at time step t
$\mathbf{f}_{e_{(k,l)}}^{(t)}$	Antenna frequency of source node of wireless link $e_{(k,l)}$ at time step t
$\mathbf{t}\mathbf{x}_{e_{(k,l)}}^{(t)}$	Transmission power of source node of wireless link $e_{(k,l)}$ at time step t
$K^{(t)}$	Number of AI services at time step t
$S^{(t)}$	Set of AI services at time step t
L_i	Number of model partitions of service s_i
$P_{s_i}^{(t)}$	Set of model partitions of service s_i
$p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$	Partition j of service s_i at time step t
$T_{s_i}^{thr(t)}$	End-to-end delay threshold of service s_i at time step t
$\mathbf{R}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$	Set of resource requirements of model partition p_{j,s_i} at time step t
$\mathbf{m}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$	Size of model partition p_{j,s_i} at time step t
$\mathbf{i}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$	Data input shape of model partition p_{j,s_i} at time step t
$\mathbf{o}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$	Data output shape of model partition p_{j,s_i} at time step t
$\mathbf{d}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$	Data sample size of model partition p_{j,s_i} at time step t
$c_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$	Complexity of model partition p_{j,s_i} at time step t
$T_{j,s_i,n}^{comp(t)}$	Computation time to execute partition $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ at network device n at time step t
$E_{j,s_i,n}^{comp(t)}$	Computation energy to execute partition $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ at network device n at time step t
$T_{(j,j+1; n_s, n_d), s_i}^{tran(t)}$	Time to transmit the output of partition $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ to the subsequent partition $p_{j+1,s_i}^{(t)}$ at time step t
$E_{(j,j+1; n_s, n_d), s_i}^{tran(t)}$	Energy to transmit the output of partition $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ to the subsequent partition $p_{j+1,s_i}^{(t)}$ at time step t

Table 1: Notation Table

4. Problem Formulation

The objective of this study is twofold. First, it aims to enable the parallel deployment of distributed AI services. Second, it aims to allocate resources to each model partition in an energy-efficient manner. The overall goal is to minimize the energy consumption of network devices hosting AI model partitions, while ensuring compliance with the end-to-end delay thresholds imposed by the AI services and network topology constraints.

Each AI model partition $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ of an AI service s_i can be deployed on any network device that meets the required resource and data requirements $R_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$. Upon deployment, an amount of the device's available resources must be allocated to support the partition execution. The latter, results in an amount of computation time and energy cost that is given by:

$$T_{j,s_i,n}^{\text{comp}(t)} = \frac{c_{j,s_i}^{(t)}}{a_n^{(t)} u_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)} f_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)}}, \quad \text{if } \Omega_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)} = 1, \quad (1)$$

$$E_{j,s_i,n}^{\text{comp}(t)} = \frac{\varsigma_n \cdot c_{j,s_i}^{(t)} \cdot (f_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)})^2}{a_n^{(t)}}, \quad \text{if } \Omega_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)} = 1 \quad (2)$$

where

$$\Omega_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if partition } p_{j,s_i}^{(t)} \in P_{s_i}^{(t)} \text{ deployed at device } n \in N \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$c_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ is the partition complexity (FLOPs), ς_n the device's effective switch capacitance, $a_n^{(t)}$ the device's FLOPs per cycle, and $u_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)}$, $f_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)}$ denote the number of CPU cores and speed per core of device n , allocated to execute model partition $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ of service s_i at time step t .

Following the execution of partition $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ of service s_i deployed at device n , its output must be transmitted to the subsequent $p_{j+1,s_i}^{(t)}$ partition. Multiple wireless links may exist between devices hosting partitions $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ and $p_{j+1,s_i}^{(t)}$. A transmission time and energy cost are introduced for each wireless link $e_{(k,l)}$ that belongs to the path connecting the host devices n_s , n_d of partitions $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ and $p_{j+1,s_i}^{(t)}$ and are given below.

$$T_{(j,j+1;n_s,n_d),s_i}^{\text{trans}(t)} = \sum_{e_{(k,l)} \in E} T_{j,s_i,e_{(k,l)}}^{\text{trans}(t)} \cdot \Omega_{e_{(k,l);n_s,n_d}}^{(t)}, \quad (4)$$

$$\text{if } \Omega_{j,s_i,n_s}^{(t)} = \Omega_{j+1,s_i,n_d}^{(t)} = 1,$$

where

$$T_{j,s_i,e(k,l)}^{tran(t)} = \frac{o_{j,s_i}^{(t)} \cdot d_{j,s_i}^{(t)}}{r_{j,s_i,e(k,l)}^{(t)}}, \quad (5)$$

$T_{j,s_i,e(k,l)}^{tran(t)}$ is the time (in *seconds*) required to transmit the output of partition $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ over $e(k,l)$; $o_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ is the output size, $d_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ is the sample precision and $o_{j,s_i}^{(t)} \cdot d_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ is the payload size to be transferred.

$$r_{j,s_i,e(k,l)}^{(t)} = \mathbf{b}_{j,s_i,n_s}^{(t)} \cdot \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{g_{e(k,l)}^{(t)} \cdot \mathbf{t}\mathbf{x}_{j,s_i,n_s}^{(t)}}{\mathbf{b}_{j,s_i,n_s}^{(t)} \cdot N_{0e(k,l)}} \right), \quad (6)$$

$r_{j,s_i,e(k,l)}^{(t)}$, $\mathbf{b}_{j,s_i,n_s}^{(t)}$ and $\mathbf{t}\mathbf{x}_{j,s_i,n_s}^{(t)}$ denote the achievable data rate of $e(k,l)$, the bandwidth and transmission power allocated to device n_s to transmit the output of partition $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ at time step t^1 , respectively;

$$g_{e(k,l)}^{(t)} = 10^{\frac{-(L_0 + 10 \cdot \mathbf{e} \cdot \log_{10}(\frac{d_{e(k,l)}}{d_0}))}{10}} \quad (7)$$

$$L_0 = 20 \cdot \log_{10}(d_0) + 20 \cdot \log_{10}(\mathbf{f}_{e(k,l)}^{(t)}) + 20 \cdot \log_{10}\left(\frac{4 \cdot \pi}{c}\right), \quad (8)$$

$$\Omega 1_{e(k,l); n_s, n_d}^{(t)} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } e(k,l) \in E \text{ belongs to path interconnecting} \\ & \text{devices } n_s \text{ and } n_d, \text{ hosts of partitions } j \text{ and } j+1, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$\Omega 1_{e(k,l); n_s, n_d}^{(t)}$ denotes whether link $e(k,l)$ belongs to the path interconnecting the host devices of the two subsequent partitions; L_0 is the path loss (in *dB*) at the reference distance d_0 (in *meters*), $d_{e(k,l)}$ is the distance between devices k and l of link $e(k,l)$ (in *meters*), \mathbf{e} is the path loss exponent and c the speed of light (in *m/s*).

Using the above, the transmission energy cost sums the per-link energy contributions based on the source transmission power $\mathbf{t}\mathbf{x}_{j,s_i,n_s}^{(t)}$ and is given

¹The same bandwidth and transmission power is applied to all devices and links belonging to the path interconnecting the host devices of two consecutive partitions.

by:

$$E_{(j,j+1; n_s, n_d), s_i}^{trans (t)} = \sum_{e(k,l) \in E} \mathbf{tx}_{j, s_i, n_s}^{(t)} \cdot T_{j, s_i, e(k,l)}^{tran (t)} \cdot \Omega_{e(k,l; n_s, n_d)}^{(t)} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{if } \Omega_{j, s_i, n_s}^{(t)} = \Omega_{j+1, s_i, n_d}^{(t)} = 1.$$

Considering the time varying number of AI services (Section 3), and the associated energy consumption within the system, our objective is to optimally select the host devices and minimize the total energy consumption per service (computational and transmission) $E_{\text{avg}}^{\text{total}(t)}$, in order to achieve balance and fairness in service execution. To this end, the formulated optimization problem is defined as follows:

$$\min_{\Omega^{(t)}, \mathbf{f}^{(t)}, \mathbf{u}^{(t)}, \mathbf{tx}^{(t)}, \mathbf{b}^{(t)}} E_{\text{avg}}^{\text{total}(t)} = \frac{\sum_{s_i \in S^{(t)}} \sum_{j, j+1 \in P_{s_i}^{(t)}} \sum_{n_s, n_d \in N} \left(E_{j, s_i, n_s}^{\text{comp} (t)} + E_{(j, j+1; n_s, n_d), s_i}^{trans (t)} \right)}{|S^{(t)}|} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{j, j+1 \in P_{s_i}^{(t)}} \sum_{n_s, n_d \in N} \left(T_{j, s_i, n_s}^{\text{comp} (t)} + T_{(j, j+1; n_s, n_d), s_i}^{tran (t)} \right) < T_{s_i}^{\text{thr} (t)}, \quad \forall s_i \quad (12)$$

$$u_n^{\min (t)} \cdot f_n^{\min (t)} \leq \sum_{s_i \in S^{(t)}} \sum_{j \in P_{s_i}^{(t)}} u_{j, s_i, n}^{(t)} \cdot f_{j, s_i, n}^{(t)} \cdot \Omega_{j, s_i, n}^{(t)} \leq u_n^{\max (t)} \cdot f_n^{\max (t)}, \quad \forall n \in N, \quad (13)$$

$$u_n^{\min (t)} \leq \sum_{s_i \in S^{(t)}} \sum_{j \in P_{s_i}^{(t)}} u_{j, s_i, n}^{(t)} \cdot \Omega_{j, s_i, n}^{(t)} \leq u_n^{\max (t)}, \quad \forall n \in N, \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{s_i \in S^{(t)}} \sum_{j \in P_{s_i}^{(t)}} \left[m_{j, s_i}^{(t)} + (\mathbf{i}_{j, s_i}^{(t)} + \mathbf{o}_{j, s_i}^{(t)}) \cdot \mathbf{d}_{j, s_i}^{(t)} \right] \cdot \Omega_{j, s_i, n}^{(t)} \leq m_n^{\max (t)}, \quad \forall n \in N, \quad (15)$$

$$\sum_{s_i \in S^{(t)}} \sum_{j \in P_{s_i}^{(t)}} \left[m_{j, s_i}^{(t)} + (\mathbf{i}_{j, s_i}^{(t)} + \mathbf{o}_{j, s_i}^{(t)}) \cdot \mathbf{d}_{j, s_i}^{(t)} \right] \cdot \Omega_{j, s_i, n}^{(t)} \leq d_n^{\max (t)}, \quad \forall n \in N, \quad (16)$$

$$\mathbf{tx}_{e(k,l)}^{\min (t)} \leq \mathbf{tx}_{j, s_i, n_s}^{(t)} \leq \mathbf{tx}_{e(k,l)}^{\max (t)}, \quad (17)$$

$$\forall s_i, j, e(k,l), n_s, n_d, \text{ if } \Omega_{e(k,l; n_s, n_d)}^{(t)} = 1,$$

$$\sum_{s_i \in S^{(t)}} \sum_{j \in P_{s_i}^{(t)}} \sum_{n_s \in N} \sum_{n_d \in N} \Lambda_{j,s_i,n_s,n_d,e_{(k,l)}}^{(t)} \cdot \mathbf{b}_{j,s_i,n_s}^{(t)} \leq \mathbf{b}_{e_{(k,l)}}^{\max (t)}, \quad \forall e_{(k,l)}, \quad (18)$$

where

$$\Lambda_{j,s_i,n_s,n_d,e_{(k,l)}}^{(t)} = \Omega_{j,s_i,n_s}^{(t)} \Omega_{j+1,s_i,n_d}^{(t)} \Omega_{1(e_{(k,l)};n_s,n_d)}^{(t)},$$

$$\sum_{n \in N} \Omega_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)} = 1, \forall j \in P_{s_i}^{(t)}, \quad (19)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\Omega}^{(t)} &= [\Omega_{1,s_1,n_i}^{(t)}, \Omega_{2,s_1,n_j}^{(t)}, \dots]^T, \quad \mathbf{f}^{(t)} = [f_{1,s_1,n_i}^{(t)}, f_{2,s_1,n_j}^{(t)}, \dots]^T, \\ \mathbf{u}^{(t)} &= [u_{1,s_1,n_i}^{(t)}, u_{1,s_1,n_j}^{(t)}, \dots]^T, \quad \mathbf{tx}^{(t)} = [\mathbf{tx}_{1,s_1,n_i}, \mathbf{tx}_{2,s_1,n_j}, \dots]^T, \\ \text{and } \mathbf{b}^{(t)} &= [\mathbf{b}_{1,s_1,n_i}^{(t)}, \mathbf{b}_{2,s_1,n_j}^{(t)}, \dots]^T, \end{aligned}$$

are the decision parameters for each partition $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)} \in P_{s_i}^{(t)}$ with $n_i, n_j \in N$.

Constraint (12) upper bounds the total time of service s_i at time t as the sum of the computation times of the placed partitions and the hop-by-hop transmission times along the selected paths. Constraints (13)-(16) ensure that the total computational capacity allocated to device n to execute all assigned partitions are within its minimum and maximum capacities. Similarly, constraints (17) and (18) ensure that the transmission power selected, and the total bandwidth allocated to device n_s to transmit the output of all assigned partitions meet its capabilities and the available bandwidth of each link $e_{(k,l)}$ that belongs to the path that interconnects devices hosting subsequent partitions at time step t . Finally, constraint (19) ensures that each service partition is deployed on exactly one device at any given time step t . It should be noted that constraints (13)-(18) and constraint (19) are considered hard constraints as they are hardware-bounded. Constraint (12) is a soft constraint that ensures timely service execution, leading to a satisfactory end-user experience.

The above formulation and analysis shows that the problem examined is of high complexity. It includes multiple optimization parameters for both AI service deployment and resource allocation for each model partition. The problem's complexity increases further when considering that a decision must be made at each time step.

Figure 1: Illustration of the Proposed HGA

5. The Proposed Hierarchical Genetic Algorithm

5.1. Overview and Key Definitions

This section introduces a custom meta-heuristic two-tier hierarchical genetic algorithm (HGA) to address the twofold objective outlined in Section 4. Genetic Algorithms (GAs) are problem-agnostic metaheuristic solvers that do not rely on the explicit state of the environment for decision-making. Instead, they evolve their strategies over time by monitoring an evaluation score, referred to as the fitness function. Building upon this problem-agnostic property, the proposed hierarchical approach adopts a divide-and-conquer strategy, splitting the original complex problem into two sequentially interdependent sub-problems of reduced computational complexity. This divide-and-conquer strategy enables the two tiers to generate efficient partial solutions that can be effectively combined to produce better decisions that evolve over time. This chain of GA based decision-making mutually contribute to the overall energy minimization of the system. Figure 1 illustrates an overview of the algorithm.

First Tier GA: The top tier of the hierarchy is responsible for decision-making regarding the optimal deployment of distributed AI services within the underlying network topology. Specifically, this tier provides *resource-*

agnostic deployment decisions, operating on an abstract view of the available devices and the links interconnecting them, without accounting for their hardware characteristics. Once the first tier GA selects the devices to host each service partition, multiple candidate paths may exist between pairs of consecutive model partitions. For each such pair of partition-hosting devices, the shortest path is determined using Dijkstra’s algorithm [30]. In particular, among the candidate paths, the one with the minimum weight, defined as the sum of the weights of its constituent links, is selected.

Second Tier GA: Based on these high-level deployment decisions, the second tier refines the solution by determining the optimal resource allocation for each model partition. Unlike the first tier, it explicitly considers the computational and communication capabilities of the selected devices, as well as the bandwidth of their connecting links. This *resource-aware* refinement ensures that the deployed partitions are not only correctly deployed within the topology but also efficiently mapped to the available hardware resources. To evaluate the effectiveness of the combined decisions of both tiers, a feedback is received through a defined fitness function that accounts for both total AI service energy consumption and latency.

The optimization in both tiers follows the same evolutionary process. Each GA strategically performs a global search by means of many local searches, generating high-quality solutions over time (generation) relying on biologically inspired operations, such as parent selection, crossover and mutation [31]. In each *generation*, each GA constructs a population of *chromosomes*, which is a set of candidate solutions to each optimization sub-problem. The target of each GA is to provide higher quality solutions over the generations using as criterion the fitness score of each chromosome, which represents the target objective of the optimization problem. The main definitions of HGA solution are provided below:

Generation: A time step t , initiating the chain of decisions.

First Tier Gene: A model partition deployment, i.e. a device selection $n \in N$ ($\Omega_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)}$) for partition $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ of service s_i .

Second Tier Gene: A resource allocation to model partition $p_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$ assigned to device n , i.e. $[f_{j,s_i,n}, u_{j,s_i,n}, \mathbf{t}x_{j,s_i,n}, \mathbf{b}_{j,s_i,n}]$, that is bounded according to constraints (13)-(18).

First/Second Tier Chromosome: A vector consisting of genes equal to the number of model partitions of all AI services $S^{(t)}$, representing a candidate solution to the first/second optimization sub-problem.

First/Second Tier Elites: The number of best-scored chromosomes in a generation that are included unaltered in the next generation.

First/Second Tier Population: A fixed-size set of first/second tier chromosomes.

Fitness Function²: A function that serves as a score for both first and second tier chromosomes and is formulated based on the objective function (11), in conjunction with the list of constraints presented in the previous section. Specifically:

$$FF^{(t)} = -[w_{ff,1} \cdot E_{\text{avg}}^{\text{total}(t)} + w_{ff,2} \cdot \mathbf{P}^{(t)}] \quad (20)$$

As $w_{ff,1}$ and $w_{ff,2}$ we denote the weights assigned to each part of the equation. The first part of Eq. (20) is the objective function of our problem formulation. The second part $\mathbf{P}^{(t)}$ is a penalty term defined to guarantee a safe HGA process [32]. Consequently, the first- and second-tier chromosomes that violate the constraints and result in infeasible solutions will be penalized. We define this penalty as follows:

$$\mathbf{P}^{(t)} = \frac{(w_1 \cdot v^{(t)} + w_2 \cdot (D_{\text{time}}^{(t)})^2 + w_3 \cdot D_{\text{res}}^{(t)} + w_4 \cdot D_{\text{link}}^{(t)} + w_5 \cdot O^{(t)})}{|S^{(t)}|}, \quad (21)$$

where:

$v^{(t)}$ denotes the total number of constraint violations resulting from the combined first- and second-tier decisions at time step t ,

$$D_{\text{time}}^{(t)} = \sum_{s_i \in S^{(t)}} (T_{s_i}^{(t)} - T_{s_i}^{\text{thr}(t)})_+, \quad (22)$$

²Each term of the fitness function is normalized according to its own scale, ensuring balanced contributions and preventing bias toward any particular constraint.

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{\text{res}}^{(t)} = \sum_{n \in N} & \left[\left(\sum_{s_i \in S^{(t)}} \sum_{j \in P_{s_i}^{(t)}} u_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)} \cdot f_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)} \cdot \Omega_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)} - u_n^{\max(t)} \cdot f_n^{\max(t)} \right) \right]_+ \\
& + \left(\sum_{s_i \in S^{(t)}} \sum_{j \in P_{s_i}^{(t)}} u_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)} \cdot \Omega_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)} - u_n^{\max(t)} \right)_+ \\
& + \left(\sum_{s_i \in S^{(t)}} \sum_{j \in P_{s_i}^{(t)}} [\mathbf{m}_{j,s_i}^{(t)} + (\mathbf{i}_{j,s_i}^{(t)} + \mathbf{o}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}) \cdot \mathbf{d}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}] \cdot \Omega_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)} - m_n^{\max(t)} \right)_+ \\
& + \left(\sum_{s_i \in S^{(t)}} \sum_{j \in P_{s_i}^{(t)}} [\mathbf{m}_{j,s_i}^{(t)} + (\mathbf{i}_{j,s_i}^{(t)} + \mathbf{o}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}) \cdot \mathbf{d}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}] \cdot \Omega_{j,s_i,n}^{(t)} - d_n^{\max(t)} \right)_+ \Big], \tag{23}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{\text{link}}^{(t)} = \sum_{e(k,l) \in E} & \left[\left(\sum_{s_i \in S^{(t)}} \sum_{j \in P_{s_i}^{(t)}} \sum_{n_s \in N} \sum_{n_d \in N} \Lambda_{j,s_i,n_s,n_d,e(k,l)}^{(t)} \cdot \mathbf{b}_{j,s_i,n_s}^{(t)} - \mathbf{b}_{e(k,l)}^{\max(t)} \right) \right]_+ \\
& + \left[\sum_{s_i \in S^{(t)}} \sum_{j \in P_{s_i}^{(t)}} \sum_{n_s \in N} \sum_{n_d \in N} \Lambda_{j,s_i,n_s,n_d,e(k,l)}^{(t)} \cdot (\mathbf{t}\mathbf{x}_{j,s_i,n_s}^{(t)} - \mathbf{t}\mathbf{x}_{e(k,l)}^{\max(t)}) \right]_+. \tag{24}
\end{aligned}$$

For reminder purposes

$$\Lambda_{j,s_i,n_s,n_d,e(k,l)}^{(t)} = \Omega_{j,s_i,n_s}^{(t)} \Omega_{j+1,s_i,n_d}^{(t)} \Omega_{1(e(k,l);n_s,n_d)}^{(t)}.$$

The $(\cdot)_+$ operator is used to penalize only when a condition exceeds the predetermined threshold. Eq. (22), based on constraint (12), defines the $D_{\text{time}}^{(t)}$ as the distance between the total time $T_{s_i}^{(t)}$ (computational and communication) required to execute service s_i and the time threshold imposed to the service at time step t . Similarly, following constraints (13)-(18), Eqs. (23) and (24) quantify the excess demand in computational (CPU cycles, CPU cores, memory and disk storage) and communication (bandwidth and transmission power) resources, respectively, relative to the maximum available capacity of each device or link. Finally, $O^{(t)}$ denotes the aggregate percentage-wise ratio of over-utilization across all devices and links, encompassing both computational and communication resources at time step t .

Figure 2: Illustration of HGA’s Methodology

It captures, the extent to which the computational and communication resources exceed their maximum available capacities. In other words, for every resource type of a device or link that operates beyond 100% of its capacity, the amount by which it exceeds this threshold is expressed as a percentage, and $O^{(t)}$ is defined as the sum of these percentages across the entire system.

5.2. Methodology

This section provides the step-by-step methodology of the proposed HGA. Figure 2 illustrates the complete process in a circular flow, highlighting the iterative solutions’ refinement across generations. The complete list of steps along with their description are provided below.

Step 1 [Initialization]: This step initiates HGA process, as it initializes the population of both first- and second- tier GAs. In this phase, a set of random chromosomes, referred to as the *initial population*, is generated for each tier. These chromosomes serve as the starting point (first generation) for subsequent evaluation and evolution.

Step 2 [First Evaluation]: This step acts as a first evaluation point for each generation. A mutual fitness score is assigned to each combination of first- and second- tier chromosomes using Eq. (20). This score guides the evolutionary process toward better quality chromosomes that satisfy the objective (Eq. (11)) and comply to constraints (12)-(19).

Step 3 [Repairing Phase]: This step introduces a custom repair mecha-

nism that facilitates the evolutionary process by contributing to constraint violations reduction. For each combination of first- and second- tier chromosomes that violates the constraints, the following actions are performed:

- Detect over-utilized devices where the assigned model partitions exceed the available computational and/or communication resources.
- Identify the violated resource types (e.g. cpu, bandwidth) of the over-utilized devices.
- Detect services that include partitions assigned to over-utilized devices and violate the time related constraint (Constraint (12)). Then, for each service locate the most time consuming partition both in terms of computation and communication.
- Attempt to repair over-utilization by applying a percentage-wise reduction to the resources allocated to the partitions of an over-utilized device, for all identified violated resource types. The located most time consuming model partitions are excluded from this process as this will introduce further delays to the related services.

Step 4 [Random Chromosome Injection]: This step contributes to avoiding premature convergence by introducing randomness to each population. At each generation, one random chromosome is injected into both the first- and second-tier populations, expanding the search space and increasing the diversity of the evolutionary process.

Step 5 [Hypermutation]: This step is triggered when the distance of the fitness score from the best-scoring chromosomes (first- and second-tier) of two consecutive generations is higher than a pre-selected percentage threshold H_{thr} . The *hypermutation* enhances evolutionary diversity by increasing percentage-wise the rate of gene alteration that is known as the *mutation rate* (See **Step 8**).

Step 6 [Fixed Memory]: This step initiates a *fixed memory* (FM) mechanism that stores the B best chromosomes found so far. With a predefined probability p_{fm} , these stored chromosomes replace the B worst chromosomes of the current generation, thereby ensuring that high-quality solutions are preserved across generations.

Step 7 [Second Evaluation]: Following **Step 6**, the resulted first- and second-tier populations, are re-evaluated using Eq. (20). After this fitness

score assignment, both populations are sorted so that the best-scoring chromosomes are placed at the top. The top *el* chromosomes, known as *elites*, are transferred unaltered to the next generation to ensure the preservation of high-quality solutions.

Step 8 [GA Operations]: In this step, the standard GA operations [33] are applied to both the first- and second-tier populations, enabling their evolution prior to transferring into the next generation. The following operations are performed:

- **Parent Selection:** In each generation, first-tier chromosomes are selected as parents (following a Roulette Wheel approach ([34])) for crossover in order to create offspring for the next generation. Following this, second-tier parent selection must be aligned with the first-tier, as second-tier resource allocation inherently depends on the first-tier device selection. The parent selection is crucial to HGA’s convergence since fit parents tend to produce better and fitter solutions.
- **Crossover:** Following parent selection, a crossover operation is applied in order to combine genetic information of the two selected parents of each tier to generate new offspring. A uniform crossover method is employed to each tier, where each gene of an offspring is inherited from one of the parents selected based on a probability p_c , referred to as the *crossover rate*.
- **Mutation:** Subsequent to offspring generation, a mutation operation is applied. Mutation enables the exploration of the search space as it randomly tweaks genes of first- and second-tier chromosomes with a probability p_m , called *mutation rate*. This results to new candidates solutions, known as *mutated chromosomes*, introducing diversity in the population.

Step 9 [New Generation Preparation]: This step concludes a generation cycle and prepares the next evolution. The first- and second-tier chromosomes produced by **Step 8** along with the elites of **Step 7** form the next generation population.

Steps 2-9 are repeated until a termination criterion is met. An early stopping mechanism interrupts the search procedure when the best-scoring combination of first- and second-tier chromosomes does not improve for a certain number of generations. This reduces unnecessary computations and contributes to faster convergence.

Offline and Online Phase: HGA consists of two phases: The offline and the online phase. During the offline phase, HGA explores different candidate solutions in each generation to converge on an optimal deployment of distributed AI services and an optimal resource allocation for each model partition within the underlying network topology. In the online phase, HGA is evaluated based on its performance in various evaluation scenarios involving semi-static and dynamic network topologies and device resource capabilities, where its strategies are applied in near real-time.

5.3. Computational Complexity

The computational cost of HGA depends on the population size P , number of generations Gn , total model partitions L , network devices N and network links E . Each generation involves fitness evaluation and GA operations for both tiers. The first-tier GA additionally performs Dijkstra’s shortest-path search for all partition pairs, resulting in a total complexity of $\mathcal{O}(L \cdot E \cdot \log N)$ [35] per generation. Accordingly, the overall time complexity of HGA is estimated as:

$$\mathcal{O}(2 \cdot P \cdot Gn \cdot (L \cdot E \cdot \log N)).$$

HGA remains tractable since P , Gn , and L (algorithmic parameters) are bounded. It should be noted that the offline phase absorbs most of the computational cost, while the online phase (with small P and Gn) achieves near real-time performance.

6. Simulation Setup

The simulation setup is comprised of 30 heterogeneous (in terms of computational and communication capabilities) devices. These devices are uniformly distributed in an area of 500 x 500 *meters*, where each device is at least 5 *meters* away from the others.

AI Services and Partitions Setup: Our evaluation setup considers up to 40 AI services, each resembling a complex Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture. These CNN models differ in the number of their layers, ranging from 40 to 80. They also differ in their data input shape $\mathbf{i}_{j,s_i}^{(t)}$, which is either [1, 3, 128, 128] or [1, 3, 224, 224] with a 32 *bits* precision. The output channels are within {16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512}. Each CNN model comprises 80% convolutional layers (*Conv2D*) and 20% pooling layers (*MaxPool2D*),

as well as up to two Fully Connected (*FC*) layers, each with 64, 128, or 256 neurons. The kernel size is either (3x3) or (5x5). As a result, each CNN model has a varying complexity ranging from 300 Mega Floating Operations (MFLOPs) to 1.4 Tera FLOPs (TFLOPs). Each CNN varies in the number of model partitions, ranging from 4 to 8. Overall in our setup, we consider the total number of model partitions ranging from 40 to 320. Finally, the end-to-end delay threshold considered for each AI service is in the range of [4, 15] *seconds*.

Device Setup: The same minimum CPU speed $f_n^{min(t)}$ is assumed for all devices equal to 0.1 *GHz*, while the maximum one $f_n^{max(t)}$ at each time step is within [3, 5.5] *GHz*. The number of CPU cores range from 64 ($u_n^{min(t)}$) to 128 ($u_n^{max(t)}$) for each device. The maximum memory $m_n^{max(t)}$ and disk storage $d_n^{max(t)}$ are within {64, 128, 256} *GB* and {100, 500, 1000} *GB*, respectively. The number of FLOPs per cycle is the same for all devices, constant across time steps t , and equal to $a_n = 32$. The effective switched capacitance applied to all devices is equal to $\varsigma_n = 10^{-28}$ *Watt/Hz³*. Regarding the communication capabilities of each device, the antenna frequency $\mathbf{f}_{e(k,l)}^{(t)}$ is within [1.8, 3.7] *GHz* and the transmission power $\mathbf{tx}_{e(k,l)}^{(t)}$ is within [10, 33] *dBm*.

Network Environment Setup: We consider a non-free space (i.e., with obstacles) environment, where a mesh network topology of devices is deployed. Although focusing on a wireless mesh topology, this setup is used only as a representative distributed environment to validate the algorithm’s behavior under heterogeneous computational and communication conditions. The proposed framework and HGA formulation are topology-independent and can be readily applied to alternative infrastructures such as O-RAN edge networks or data center fabrics with programmable hardware. We set the reference distance $d_0 = 1$ *meter*, a constant path loss exponent $\mathbf{e} = 1.5$ and the same constant Gaussian noise power spectral density $N_{0e} = -158$ *dBm/Hz* applied to each link e of the topology. The spectral efficiency assumed for each link e is equal to 4 *bits/Hz*. The maximum available bandwidth at time step t $\mathbf{b}_{e(k,l)}^{(t)}$ allocated to each link $e_{(k,l)}$ is in the range of [80, 100] *MHz*. Two different network environments are considered in all performed experiments, in order to showcase the robustness of our HGA, namely a semi-static and a dynamic network environment. Four total evaluation scenarios are considered for both environments, differing in the maximum number of AI services, which is 10, 20, 30 and 40, respectively.

Semi-Static Environment Setup: In the semi-static environment, ev-

Scenario	AI Services			
	10	20	30	40
Population Size	250			
Elites (el)	80			
Crossover Rate (p_c)	0.1			
Mutation Rate (p_m)	0.1			
Mutation Decay Rate	0.995			
Hypermutation Threshold (H_{thr})	0.1			
FM Replacement Rate (p_{fm})	0.8			
FM Size (B)	10			

Table 2: HGA Configuration Setup

ery 10 time steps, each AI service considered in each scenario has a 5% probability of being deactivated/activated, altering the system load. However, the device and network network environment setups are initialized within the afore-described ranges and remain constant across time steps.

Dynamic Environment Setup: In the dynamic environment, every 10 time steps the number of active AI services and the network conditions change. More specifically, each AI service considered in each scenario has a 10% probability of being deactivated/activated. Each device and wireless link in the network has a 30% probability of changing its resource availability within the previously described ranges.

6.1. HGA Setup

The proposed HGA was realized through a fully custom Python implementation. Table 2 includes the configuration setup applied to both tiers of HGA and was used for all scenarios and in all evaluation experiments. The maximum number of generations is set to 1500, with early stopping triggered after 200 consecutive non-improving generations. The mutation rate, linearly decays at each generation. When the hyper-mutation is triggered, the mutation rate is increased by 50%. The weights defined in equations (20) and (21) are experimentally tuned and configured as $w_{ff,1} = 0.6$, $w_{ff,2} = 0.4$, $w_1 = 0.26$, $w_2 = 0.26$, $w_3 = 0.16$, $w_4 = 0.16$, and $w_5 = 0.16$.

7. Evaluation Results

This section provides numerical results to assess the performance and robustness of the proposed HGA, as well as its comparative performance against two state-of-the-art baselines, under the network environments and evaluation scenarios presented in Section 6. Three main performance metrics

are considered: **1)** the per AI service energy consumption, **2)** the per AI service end-to-end (E2E) latency, **3)** the total number of constraint violations (including hard and soft constraints).

7.1. Offline Phase

Figure 3: Offline phase of the proposed HGA for different number of AI services.

The first set of the evaluation results concerns the offline phase of HGA. This offline phase was conducted within the dynamic network environment and across different evaluation scenarios. The introduced diversity enables robust tuning and enhances the generalization capabilities of the chained GA decision-making.

Fig. 3 illustrates the performance of HGA, considering different number of AI services ($|\mathcal{S}| = \{10, 20, 30, 40\}$), as the generations evolve. Fig. 3a depicts the evolution of the fitness score across generations. The results indicate that HGA achieves high performance (observed after roughly 125 generations, indicated by the fitness score approaching zero) under network dynamicity and for the different number of AI services considered, demonstrating robustness and stability, as well as effective cooperation between the two GA tiers.

Fig. 3b depicts the per AI service energy consumption, i.e. the average of the total computation and transmission energy across all services. As it can be inferred from the figure, the amount of consumed energy, for the different number of AI services, significantly decreases with the number of generations. In addition, the figure illustrates the capability of HGA to achieve similar energy per AI service, regardless of the number of AI services. Fluctuations

in the average energy consumption are observed. These can be attributed to the variations in the number of active AI services and the constantly changing network conditions. However, the amplitude of these fluctuations is highly constrained, showcasing the ability of HGA to find suitable strategies regardless of the environment dynamicity. These results indicate both an effective deployment strategy (first-tier GA) and efficient per model partition resource allocation (second-tier GA). In particular, the overall energy reductions (between the first and the last generation) are up to 86.5%, 87.9%, 93.5%, and 96.8% for 10, 20, 30, and 40 AI services, respectively.

As already stated, the current work introduced a penalty function toward a *safe* HGA process. Accordingly, Fig. 3c depicts the total number of constraint violations, including both soft and hard ones, across generations. The results show an effective and efficient chained decision-making between the two GA tiers, as the total number of violations is (eventually, after a number of generations) eliminated in all evaluation scenarios. Despite the dynamicity in network conditions and AI services, HGA consistently converges to *safe* decision-making, enabling an efficient distributed AI service execution, while respecting the hardware-related constraints and the imposed end-to-end latency threshold.

To summarize, during the offline phase, HGA showcases scalable performance (yielding similar results upon convergence) despite variations in the network conditions and number of active AI services. The divide-and-conquer strategy introduced by our two-tier HGA, enables effective cooperation, leading to a per service energy consumption and violations-free chained decision-making that is comparable across all evaluation scenarios.

7.2. Online Phase and Baselines Comparison

The second round of results includes the evaluation of the performance and generalization capabilities of HGA against two state-of-the-art baseline algorithms. The online phase is carried out using both semi-static and dynamic network environments and evaluation scenarios. It should be noted that all statistical results are averaged, over 100 independent experiments, in order to draw accurate conclusions.

The transition to the online phase requires to preserve the latest population of HGA’s offline phase and set it as a starting point for potential further evolution. To achieve near real-time decision-making, the population size, number of elites, and number of generations are set to 20, 2, and 5, respectively. This significantly reduces the computational complexity of

the algorithm without compromising its adaptability to new conditions. We compare our HGA solution against a custom Epsilon Greedy and a Vanilla Genetic Algorithm, two baseline solutions used in state-of-the-art related works [36, 37, 38]. In order to achieve a fair comparison, both baselines were transformed to their two-tier hierarchical counterparts following the same approach with HGA. The Vanilla Genetic Algorithm has the exact configuration with HGA, whereas the ϵ of Epsilon Greedy is set to 0.05, corresponding to a 5% probability of exploring random strategies and a 95% probability of exploiting the best-performing ones.

- **Hierarchical Epsilon Greedy (HEG):** At each time step, the HEG selects the AI service deployment decision and resource allocation across model partitions that led to the best outcome so far, based on the fitness score (Eq. (20)).
- **Hierarchical Vanilla Genetic Algorithm (HVGA):** HVGA is the simplest form of HGA, integrating only the basic operations of a genetic algorithm (i.e., parent selection, crossover and mutation).

Table 3 presents the performance comparison of our solution, against the baselines under different network environments and scenarios, with regard to: **1)** the average (per AI service) total, computation and transmission energy (in *Joules*), **2)** the average end-to-end, computation and transmission delay (in *seconds*), **3)** the total number of soft and hard constraint violations.

As it can be deduced from the table, our proposed solution outperforms the considered baseline algorithms, in terms of the consumed energy, regardless of the number of AI services and network environment dynamicity. More specifically, HGA manages to reduce the total per AI service energy consumption by 43.9%, 82.9%, 83.3% and 82.6% compared to HVGA and by 94.1%, 93%, 89.6% and 88.4% compared to HEG, for the 10, 20, 30 and 40 AI services in the semi-static environment. In the same notion, HGA manages a reduction in the total per AI service energy consumption by 43.4%, 82.6%, 86.6% and 81.2% compared to HVGA and by 94.1%, 92.6%, 89.7% and 88.9% compared to HEG, for the 10, 20, 30 and 40 AI services in the dynamic environment. In the case of the 10 AI services, both HGA and VHGA demonstrate comparable performance, underscoring the general effectiveness of GAs. However, VHGA underperforms in the remaining evaluation scenarios, thereby emphasizing the need for robust and adaptive mechanisms such as those proposed in this study (i.e., repairing mechanism, custom

penalty function). Focusing on the transmission energy and delay, an increase with the number of AI services (and consequently model partitions) is observed. This relies on the fact that in order to avoid per device resource over-provisioning, sequentially connected model partitions must be distributed across multiple devices, which results in higher communication energy and time costs.

It is important to note that although it seems that HVGA and HEG outperform our solution in terms of end-to-end delay per service, the number of total violations (and most importantly the hard ones), indicate completely infeasible strategies. The absence of a repairing mechanism in both baseline solutions leads to higher resource allocation per model partition, which exceeds device resource availability but, consequently, results in lower end-to-end delay. Especially in the case of 40 services, both HVGA and HEG reach the staggering number of 71 and 100 hard violations, respectively. In contrast, our HGA achieves a fully feasible strategy (no hard violations) with almost zero soft violations in all evaluation scenarios and environments, through the integration of a repairing mechanism and a penalty function.

In summary, the proposed HGA approach is proven to be safe and energy efficient, regardless of the complexity of the problem. It completely respects system constraints and provides reasonable trade-off between energy consumption and end-to-end delay, while outperforming the two state-of-the-art baselines.

8. Conclusions

This paper proves the effectiveness and feasibility of the proposed hierarchical genetic algorithm (HGA) for energy-efficient distributed AI service deployment and execution while meeting service latency requirements. The custom meta-heuristic two-tier HGA adopts a divide-and-conquer strategy to provide joint placement decisions, adapted to service availability, time-varying device computational and communication resources, and network conditions. The feasibility of HGA’s chained decision-making is ensured by introducing a custom repairing mechanism and a penalty function. The model parameters and algorithms are designed to be agnostic to network structure, allowing straightforward adaptation to other architectures. Evaluation results showcase the superiority of our approach compared to a heuristic hierarchical greedy algorithm and a hierarchical vanilla genetic algorithm, achieving up to 94.1% reduction in total energy consumption per service,

Semi - Static Network Environment							Dynamic Network Environment					
	10 AI Services			20 AI Services			10 AI Services			20 AI Services		
	HGA	VHGA	HEG	HGA	VHGA	HEG	HGA	VHGA	HEG	HGA	VHGA	HEG
Total AVG. Energy (J)	0.278	0.496	4.753	0.286	1.675	4.114	0.288	0.509	4.932	0.29	1.669	3.967
Computation Energy (J)	0.26	0.486	4.671	0.182	1.641	3.845	0.27	0.498	4.858	0.171	1.636	3.700
Transmission Energy (J)	0.018	0.010	0.083	0.105	0.034	0.269	0.018	0.010	0.074	0.119	0.033	0.267
E2E Delay (s)	1.031	1.200	0.588	1.39	1.984	0.639	1.086	1.213	0.593	1.316	2.009	0.652
Computation Delay (s)	0.900	0.991	0.304	0.845	1.897	0.340	0.952	1.004	0.336	0.83	1.922	0.348
Transmission Delay (s)	0.131	0.209	0.284	0.545	0.086	0.299	0.133	0.209	0.258	0.486	0.087	0.304
Soft Violations	0.00	0.00	0.19	0.00	2.820	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.22	0.00	2.710	0.00
Hard Violations	0.00	0.00	37.25	0.00	26.840	61.87	0.00	0.00	34.60	0.00	24.740	59.26

	30 AI Services			40 AI Services			30 AI Services			40 AI Services		
Energy (J)	0.240	1.439	2.329	0.286	1.653	2.472	0.245	1.836	2.380	0.272	1.454	2.471
Computation Energy (J)	0.212	1.407	2.200	0.126	1.618	2.436	0.222	1.814	2.261	0.126	1.420	2.434
Transmission Energy (J)	0.028	0.032	0.129	0.160	0.034	0.036	0.023	0.022	0.119	0.146	0.034	0.037
E2E Delay (s)	2.328	0.851	0.514	3.584	2.085	0.290	2.213	2.010	0.499	3.567	0.836	0.302
Computation Delay (s)	2.067	0.749	0.373	2.958	2.000	0.150	2.010	1.853	0.357	2.968	0.734	0.173
Transmission Delay (s)	0.262	0.102	0.141	0.626	0.085	0.140	0.202	0.157	0.142	0.599	0.102	0.129
Soft Violations	0.80	0.000	0.01	0.10	2.938	0.01	0.61	1.770	0.00	0.15	0.00	0.02
Hard Violations	0.00	74.430	90.30	0.00	26.312	101.66	0.0	57.580	89.19	0.0	71.470	100.55

Table 3: Comparison between our proposed solution (HGA) and 2 state-of-the-art baselines

while completely eliminating infeasible strategies. Future work includes investigating non-sequentially connected AI services (including parallel partition executions) and integrating renewable energy sources into the system to enable greener communications.

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References

- [1] A. Hecker, C. J. Bernardos, A. Gavras, K. Schörner, R. Bou Roupahel, M. AL-Naday, C. Lombardo, M. Ghoraihi, Sustainability of 6g:

- Ways to reduce energy consumption, Tech. rep., Zenodo (2024).
doi:10.5281/zenodo.13986789.
URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13986789>
- [2] U. of Oulu, 6g white paper on edge intelligence, Tech. Rep. 8, Oulu, Finland, white paper / technical report (Jun. 2020).
URL <https://www.6gchannel.com/portfolio-posts/6g-white-paper-edge-intelligence/>
- [3] one6G Association, 6g technology overview, Tech. Rep. Fourth Edition (September 2024).
URL <https://one6g.org/download/5013/?tmstv=1725618530>
- [4] one6G Association, 6g vertical use cases, Tech. Rep. First Edition (June 2022).
URL <https://one6g.org/download/2027/>
- [5] O. Nassef, W. Sun, H. Purmehdi, M. Tatipamula, T. Mahmoodi, A survey: Distributed machine learning for 5g and beyond, *Computer Networks* 207 (2022) 108820.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2022.108820>.
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1389128622000421>
- [6] ETSI, 5G; Architecture enhancements for 5G System (5GS) to support network data analytics services (3GPP TS 23.288 version 17.4.0 Release 17), Technical Specification ETSI TS 123 288 V17.4.0 (May 2022).
- [7] 3GPP, 3rd Generation Partnership Project; Technical Specification Group Services and System Aspects; Study of Enablers for Network Automation for the 5G System (5GS); Phase 3 (Release 18), Technical Report 3GPP TR 23.700-81 (May 2022).
- [8] 3GPP, 3rd Generation Partnership Project; Technical Specification Group Services and System Aspects; Study on AI/ML Model Transfer Phase 2 (Release 19), Technical Report 3GPP TR 22.876 V19.1.0 (September 2023).
- [9] International Energy Agency (IEA), Energy and ai, Tech. rep., International Energy Agency, world Energy Outlook Special Report (Apr.

2025).

URL <https://www.iea.org/reports/energy-and-ai>

- [10] S. Niknam, H. S. Dhillon, J. H. Reed, Federated learning for wireless communications: Motivation, opportunities, and challenges, *IEEE Communications Magazine* 58 (6) (2020) 46–51. doi:10.1109/MCOM.001.1900461.
- [11] A. Vaswani, N. Shazeer, N. Parmar, J. Uszkoreit, L. Jones, A. N. Gomez, L. Kaiser, I. Polosukhin, Attention is all you need, NIPS’17, Curran Associates Inc., Red Hook, NY, USA, 2017, p. 6000–6010.
- [12] 6G-IA Vision Working Group, European vision for the 6g network ecosystem, White paper, version 2.0, 6G-IA (6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association), dissemination level: Public (Nov. 2024). doi:10.5281/zenodo.13708424.
URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13708424>
- [13] G. Premsankar, B. Ghaddar, Energy-efficient service placement for latency-sensitive applications in edge computing, *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 9 (18) (2022) 17926–17937. doi:10.1109/JIOT.2022.3162581.
- [14] A. Ben Sada, A. Khelloufi, A. Naouri, H. Ning, S. Dheilim, Energy-aware selective inference task offloading for real-time edge computing applications, *IEEE Access* 12 (2024) 72924–72937. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3404272.
- [15] Y. Bao, Y. Peng, C. Wu, Deep learning-based job placement in distributed machine learning clusters with heterogeneous workloads, *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking* 31 (2) (2023) 634–647. doi:10.1109/TNET.2022.3202529.
- [16] N. Davis, A. Brown, L. Smith, E. Wilson, O. Miller, S. Lopez, Evaluating energy-efficient device placement for distributed machine learning (01 2025). doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.13305.58722.
- [17] J. Li, F. Lin, L. Yang, D. Huang, Ai service placement for multi-access edge intelligence systems in 6g, *IEEE Transactions on Network Science and Engineering* 10 (3) (2023) 1405–1416. doi:10.1109/TNSE.2022.3228815.

- [18] Y. Chai, K. Gao, G. Zhang, L. Lu, Q. Li, Y. Zhang, Joint task offloading, resource allocation and model placement for ai as a service in 6g network, *IEEE Transactions on Services Computing* 17 (6) (2024) 3830–3843. doi:10.1109/TSC.2024.3451170.
- [19] Z. Lin, S. Bi, Y.-J. A. Zhang, Optimizing ai service placement and resource allocation in mobile edge intelligence systems, *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications* 20 (11) (2021) 7257–7271. doi:10.1109/TWC.2021.3081991.
- [20] W. Zhang, S. Zeadally, W. Li, H. Zhang, J. Hou, V. C. M. Leung, Edge ai as a service: Configurable model deployment and delay-energy optimization with result quality constraints, *IEEE Transactions on Cloud Computing* 11 (2) (2023) 1954–1969. doi:10.1109/TCC.2022.3175725.
- [21] S. Zhu, K. Ota, M. Dong, Energy-efficient artificial intelligence of things with intelligent edge, *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 9 (10) (2022) 7525–7532. doi:10.1109/JIOT.2022.3143722.
- [22] Y. Sun, J. Qiu, G. Pan, S. Xu, S. Zhang, X. Wang, S. Han, Energy optimization of multitask dnn inference in mec-assisted xr devices: A lyapunov-guided reinforcement learning approach, *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 12 (11) (2025) 17499–17513. doi:10.1109/JIOT.2025.3536879.
- [23] R. Addanki, S. B. Venkatakrishnan, S. Gupta, H. Mao, M. Alizadeh, *Placeto: learning generalizable device placement algorithms for distributed machine learning*, Curran Associates Inc., Red Hook, NY, USA, 2019.
- [24] B. Zhang, H. Zhu, F. Gao, Z. Yang, S. X. Wang, *Moirai: Towards optimal placement for distributed inference on heterogeneous devices* (2023). arXiv:2312.04025.
URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2312.04025>
- [25] S. Tuli, G. Casale, N. R. Jennings, *Splitplace: Ai augmented splitting and placement of large-scale neural networks in mobile edge environments*, *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing* 22 (9) (2023) 5539–5554. doi:10.1109/TMC.2022.3177569.

- [26] D. Katare, M. Zhou, Y. Chen, M. Janssen, A. Y. Ding, Energy-aware vision model partitioning for edge ai, in: Proceedings of the 40th ACM/SIGAPP Symposium on Applied Computing, SAC '25, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2025, p. 671–678. doi:10.1145/3672608.3707792.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3672608.3707792>
- [27] Q. Zeng, Y. Du, K. Huang, K. K. Leung, Energy-efficient resource management for federated edge learning with cpu-gpu heterogeneous computing, IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications 20 (12) (2021) 7947–7962. doi:10.1109/TWC.2021.3088910.
- [28] N. Koursioupas, L. Magoula, N. Petropoulos, A.-I. Thanopoulos, T. Panagea, N. Alonistioti, M. A. Gutierrez-Estevez, R. Khalili, A safe deep reinforcement learning approach for energy efficient federated learning in wireless communication networks, IEEE Transactions on Green Communications and Networking 8 (4) (2024) 1862–1874. doi:10.1109/TGCN.2024.3372695.
- [29] L. Magoula, N. Koursioupas, A.-I. Thanopoulos, T. Panagea, N. Petropoulos, M. A. Gutierrez-Estevez, R. Khalili, A safe genetic algorithm approach for energy efficient federated learning in wireless communication networks, in: 2023 IEEE 34th Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC), 2023, pp. 1–6. doi:10.1109/PIMRC56721.2023.10293863.
- [30] E. W. Dijkstra, A note on two problems in connexion with graphs, Numerische mathematik 1 (1) (1959) 269–271.
- [31] S. Mirjalili, Genetic Algorithm, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2019, pp. 43–55. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-93025-1_4.
URL https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-93025-1_4
- [32] J. García, F. Fernández, A comprehensive survey on safe reinforcement learning, J. Mach. Learn. Res. 16 (1) (2015) 1437–1480.
- [33] J. H. Holland, Genetic algorithms, Scientific American 267 (1) (1992) 66–73.
URL <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24939139>
- [34] B. Thomas, Evolutionary algorithms in theory and practice (1996) 120.

- [35] T. H. Cormen, C. E. Leiserson, R. L. Rivest, C. Stein, Introduction to Algorithms, 4th Edition, MIT Press, 2022.
- [36] C. C. Coskun, E. Ayanoglu, A greedy algorithm for energy-efficient base station deployment in heterogeneous networks, in: 2015 IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC), 2015, pp. 7–12. doi:10.1109/ICC.2015.7248290.
- [37] L. Magoula, S. Barmounakis, I. Stavrakakis, N. Alonistioti, A genetic algorithm approach for service function chain placement in 5g and beyond, virtualized edge networks, Computer Networks 195 (2021) 108157. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2021.108157>.
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1389128621002176>
- [38] L. Magoula, N. Koursiumpas, A.-I. Thanopoulos, T. Panagea, N. Petropoulos, M. A. Gutierrez-Estevez, R. Khalili, A safe genetic algorithm approach for energy efficient federated learning in wireless communication networks, in: 2023 IEEE 34th Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC), 2023, pp. 1–6. doi:10.1109/PIMRC56721.2023.10293863.